

Received: 15 August 2021/ Accepted: 20 August 2021/ Published: 30 August 2021
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5374641>

A critical review on minimum quantity lubrication using biodegradable hybrid nano fluids of machining operation

Dattatraya P. Kshirsagar, M.A. Venkatesh*

Amrutvahini College of Engineering, Sangmner, Ahemed Nagar, 422605, India
*Corresponding author: M. A. Venkatesh (mavenka@gmail.com)

This work was presented at the International Online Conference on Nano Materials (ICN 2021) held during 9 – 11, April 2021 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India, 686560

Abstract: Turning is one of the key and crucial processes of metal removal in industry. Increasing pollution preventing initiatives world over and consumer focus on environmentally conscious products has put increased pressure on industries to minimize or eliminate the use of cutting fluids. In the present study carried out the review work should be given to research topics aiming at the selection of hybrid nano materials and vegetable oil with the combination of biodegradable hybrid nano fluid using Minimum Quantity Lubrication assisted with turning operation based on the AISI 1040 steel.

Introduction: Machining is one of the Significant and influence task on the manufacturing industries. The industries is been using the conventional cutting fluids like oil based and water based fluids , to lubricate and cool the cutting zone . To further enhance the sustainability of Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) technique, many researchers have tried conventional cutting fluids, the requirement for attaining eco-innovativeness in manufacturing is presently recognized, and challenging noteworthy investigation efforts are anticipate. In numerous study have been aimed to MQL process in machining application, by using the new class biodegradable hybrid nano fluids as a coolant on turning operation of AISI 1040 steel using Minimum Quantity Lubrication.

Methods: The most researchers have reported on the work of vegetable oil in machining operation as coolant. Such as Rapeseed oil, Palm oil, Peanut oil, Coconut oil, Castor oil, Jatropha oil, soybean oil, sunflower oil etc. Minimum Quantity Lubrication is sustainable lubrication mechanism for implementing the usage of Hybrid Biodegradable Nanofluid, effective Minimum Quantity Lubrication system need to be developed. AISI 1040 medium carbon steel have been widely used for various industrial applications.

Conclusions: Most researchers have developed their own MQL system and integrating it with either cleaning jet, electrostatic or ultrasonic vibration. In this review articles reveals experiments conducted were mostly on Ti6Al4V, AISI 4340 steel, Inconel 718 and AISI 1045 steel and better removal of chips and other significant benefits in the performance namely, even better surface quality, less tool wear and cutting force in comparison with a stand-alone MQL system.

Keywords: *MQL, hybrid nano fluids, turning, vegetable oil*

Acknowledgment: *We are thankful to Savtribai Phule Pune University, pune for providing the technical and resources support to carry out this research work. We are also thankful to research centre at Amrutvahini College of Engineering, Sangamner, dist. Ahmednagar (M.S.). India.*

References

1. Mechiri Sandeep Kumar, V Murali Krishna , An Investigation on Turning AISI 1018 Steel with Hybrid Biodegradeable Nanofluid/MQL Incorporated with Combinations of CuO-Al₂O₃ Nanoparticles , Materials Today: Proceedings 24 (2020) 1577–1584
2. Le Gong, Rachele Bertolini, Andrea Ghiotti, Sustainable turning of Inconel 718 nickel alloy using MQL strategy based ographene nanofluids , The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology , 2020

